

Frank Starling Law (length-tension relationship) from z-bands storing retractive force

Johan Nygren, johanngrn@gmail.com

How stretched cardiac muscle is at contraction varies, since the amount of ventricular filling varies based on demand of body. Therefore, the heart sarcomeres are not at their ideal length-tension relationship when ventricular filling is less than what the body has evolved to expect that it has to be when demands are higher.

The discovery in the 1950s of the sliding filament mechanism in the sarcomere, and later advances into Huxley's model of the cross-bridge cycle, is now known to be caused by the thick and thin filament rotating into one another, like a screw in a plug (Jarosch, 2008). This can be easily seen with electron microscope, is self-evident, and models the data perfectly. Knowing this, the z-bands function is clear, they store retractive force for relaxing the muscle, through twisting the thin filaments fibers around one another.

Figure 7. Z-band dynamics. Two Z-filaments only are used per thin filament.

(a), (b) and (d) Models of narrow Z-bands with one zigzag layer only. The relaxed stage A is also shown in (c) from a guppy muscle (electron micrograph from Yamaguchi *et al.* [53]; with permission). Note that the structure of the isometric stage D in (b) has a weaker consistence against lateral influences than the stages A or G. (e) Model with two zigzag layers (from Jarosch [74]). The arrows indicate the sites where Z-filaments can wind about thin filaments. For more details see the text.

Knowing this, stretching the sarcomere could have the opposite effect, twisting the z-bands in the opposite direction, and this retractive force adds on the contractile force of the sarcomere, increasing contractility in stretched fibers as per Frank Starling's Law.

Figure 2. The thin filaments slide by using the mechanics of a drill-borer.

(a) Surface view of a reconstruction of a thin filament of frog skeletal muscle in EGTA, and (b) of *Limulus* muscle in Ca²⁺. The bright structures wound about the right-handed helical actin filaments are the two tropomyosin coiled-coils, that in (b) are shifted a little to the left. Arrow A₀ indicates the position without Ca²⁺, arrow A_i the position with Ca²⁺ (from Vibert *et al.* [35], with permission). (c) Screw of a right-handed drill-borer, shown in (d) and (e). The inclination angle of the thin filament helix and drill-borer screw is about 70°. (d) The drill-borer works by moving up and down (arrows) the handle with a nut-coil. This causes clockwise and counter-clockwise rotation (arrows) of the screw. (e) When the handle with the nut-coil is fixed, pulling up the screw

References

- Jarosch, R. (2008). Large-scale Models Reveal the Two-component Mechanics of Striated Muscle. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, *9*(12), 2658–2723.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms9122658>